
TIBETAN ARTIFACTS: PRAYER WHEELS, WORN RELIGIOUS ITEMS, TIBETAN TENTS, AND PERSONAL ORNAMENTS IN 2022

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ABSTRACT

Personal experiences and histories of local older Tibetan religious practitioners illustrate the religious and cultural practices of Stag lung Mtha' ba, Khang sar Township, Gcig sgril (Jiuzhi) County, Mgo log (Goulou) Tibetan Autonomous Prefecture, Mtsho sngon (Qinghai) Province, PR China. Highlighting the significant roles that religious items, personal ornaments, Tibetan tents, and the memories of their use play in local lives, the article provides insights into the importance of the community's religion and traditions. Interviews with local elders about their life experiences, religious items, and personal ornaments enrich our understanding of how symbols of faith connect individuals to their cultural heritage and history, offering a deeper appreciation of the significance of these items, including their symbolism and function. By showcasing the importance of personal experiences and histories in understanding the significance of religious practices and objects in a specific Tibetan community, this paper contributes to the literature on Tibetan religion and culture, offering a unique perspective on the diverse and rich traditions locally maintained and practiced and highlighting the importance of cultural heritage and history in shaping local identity and values.

KEYWORDS

thar 'khor, Tibetan artifacts, Tibetan prayer wheels, A mdo (Amdo) Tibetan, 'Jam dbyangs skyabs, Mtsho sngon (Qinghai), Gcig sgril (Jiuzhi), Stag lung Monastery, *thar mdo*, *sbra leb*, *nag tshang*

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INTRODUCTION

In exploring various aspects of Tibetan material culture, including prayer wheels and other religious items, yak hair tents, and personal ornaments, this paper seeks to deepen our understanding of Tibetan culture and society by analyzing these objects and their cultural significance. The paper draws on ethnographic research conducted in a Tibetan area of China from 2020-2023 and historical and cultural studies of Tibetan material culture. Part of this research was based on semi-structured, in-depth interviews with five Tibetans, participant observations of their everyday lives, and abridged versions of autobiographical narratives these elders provided. All interlocutors lived in Stag lung Mtha' ba¹ and were natives of Gcig sgril (Jiuzhi) County, Mgo log (Goulou) Tibetan Autonomous Prefecture, Mtsho sngon (Qinghai) Province, PR China.

While the literature on Tibetan prayer wheels already exists, for example, Google Scholar lists 242 results for "Tibetan prayer wheels,"² several of these articles are largely descriptive (Stanley 1868, Martin 1987, Modi 1918, Ladner 2000, and Winder 1992). There appears to be a dearth of studies focusing on the meaning of prayer wheels to individual Tibetan religious practitioners and the history of this meaning and practice.

In Part One, I introduce Don skyid (b. 1946), who shares the

¹ About 300 people lived in Stag lung Mtha' ba in 2023. Most were older parents and grandparents of adjacent Stag lung Monastery monks and *bla ma*. Many residents spent time circumambulating the entire monastery and temples, large Buddha images, and stupas within the monastery; prostrating to stupas and Buddha images; attending teachings by monastery *bla ma*; and joining monastery rituals. Stag lung Mtha' ba residents refer to where they live as "Mtha' ba" to local people and "Stag lung Mtha' ba" when, for example, they visit other monasteries in the area when asked where they are from. In this text, I refer to Stag lung Mtha' ba as "Mtha' ba Community." See <https://bit.ly/42HNzNz> 17 May 2023) for a discussion of *mtha' ba 'tsowa'* in A mdo and details on the "Eight Lhadé Tsowa" for a monastery in present-day Khri ka (Trika, Guide) County, Mtsho sngon Province.

² <https://bit.ly/3nRpapD> 12 May 2023.

story of her most prized possession – a *thar 'khor* 'prayer wheel'.¹ In Part Two, Don skyid describes her family's *seng gdong srung bzlog 'khor lo* prayer wheel, the history of its acquisition, how it is used, and why.

Part Three sketches the lives of Chos mdzad (b. 1938) and his wife, Yi po (b. 1941), and describes their prayer wheels, including a *thar 'khor*, two *sgrol ma'i 'khor lo*, a *ma Ni' 'khor lo*, and a *'then 'khor*.

Part Four outlines Bde sgrol's (b. 1947) life and describes her *yig brgya'i 'khor lo'*.

Part Five examines the religious items Don skyid wears, and Part Six gives the history of her family's housing (tents and houses).

Part Seven focuses on Tshe brtan's (b. 1968) life and the background of his precious *mchong 'agate'* his father gave him that he wears around his neck.

Collectively, these personal experiences and histories of local elderly Tibetan religious practitioners provide insights into Mtha' ba Community culture, highlighting the significant roles that religious items and personal ornaments play in the lives of locals.

The Appendix provides a list of relevant monasteries (Table 1), place names (Table 2), and people (Table 3).

The terms used in this paper are what I was told by the elders I interviewed. I do not represent them as "standard" and representative of life and religious practice throughout the vast area where Tibetans live.

¹ A *'khor lo* 'prayer wheel' containing a *Thar mdo* scripture is a *thar 'khor*.

MAPS

FIG 1. PR China.¹

FIG 2. A map of Mtsho sngon (Qinghai) Province.²

¹ Edited version of <https://bit.ly/42W1jnv> 15 May 2023.

² Edited version of <https://bit.ly/3nTtDbr> 15 May 2023.

FIG 3. Counties in Mgo log Tibetan Autonomous Prefecture.¹

FIG 4. Mtha' ba Community and Stag lung Monastery.²

PART ONE: DON SKYID'S THAR 'KHOR 'PRAYER WHEEL':

¹ Edited version of <https://bit.ly/2OyoZ6g> 15 May 2023.

² The map is an edited version of <https://bit.ly/3LZhJ7L>. Mtha' ba Community is inside the red outline. The monastery is within the orange outline.

"IT MEANS EVERYTHING TO ME"

Don skyid summarizes her life; the prayer wheel's history, value, and restoration in 2021; and how her attitude toward jewelry changed. Two of her sons (Phyogs las rnam rgyal (b. 1971) and Snang gsal rgya mtsho (b. 1987) live near her in Stag lung Monastery.

DON SKYID'S THAR 'KHOR

FIG 5. Don skyid with a prayer wheel at her home near Stag lung Monastery (2022, 'Jam dbyangs skyabs).

FIG 6. Don skyid with the *thar 'khor* at her home near Stag lung Monastery (2022, 'Jam dbyangs skyabs).

FIG 7. Parts of the *thar 'khor*: (1) *gnam 'khor lo rtse dgu* 'top cover', (2) *sked thag* 'silver band', (3) *tog* 'top', (4) *dong tse* 'coins',¹ (5) *sa pad+ma 'dab brgyad* 'soil, eight-leaved lotus', (6) *'khor lte*² 'rotating sleeve', (7) *'khor lo'i yu ba* 'handle', and (8) *'khor rdo* 'prayer wheel stone' (2022, 'Jam dbyangs skyabs).³

¹ See <https://tinyurl.com/3sjef5t5> 11 August 2023 (posted by Trine Brox), which discusses "prayer wheel wear pads" in Lha sa and Kathmandu.

² This *'khor lte* is made of yak horn and turns with the prayer wheel atop a coin that eventually becomes very thin (wears out) and the opening widens that the prayer wheel's central pillar passes through.

³ A weight that aids the prayer wheel's rotation. The green (imitation) turquoise also serves as a weight aiding the prayer wheel's rotation.

Religious practice is significant in Don skyid's life. The following account is a personal narrative of a Tibetan woman's life, experiences, and beliefs. It provides insight into her daily routine, family life, religious practices, and cultural traditions. This account also describes her poverty-stricken early life, her marriage arranged by family members, and her struggle to survive while raising eight children. This provides cultural and historical context, such as restrictions on religious activities during certain periods and the value placed on hard work by Tibetan society.

Overall, this narrative offers a personal and intimate look into the life and beliefs of a Tibetan woman and provides a perspective on Tibetan culture and traditions.

DON SKYID'S ACCOUNT: A PRAYER WHEEL AND HER LIFE

This '*khor lo* 'prayer wheel' is my only precious thing. I used to have a few ornaments. My parents and husband (Bsod dar, 1943-2016) gave me some, and I bought some. I spin my '*khor lo* early every morning while chanting *Yig brgya*

'Hundred Syllable Mantra'¹ for about an hour. Other than that, I don't have a specific time for spinning my '*khor lo*, but sometimes I spin it later in the day when I am free.

My husband and I were very poor when we first married. Three yaks were all we had. My husband's cousin ('Phrin las rgya mtsho 19?? -1970)² and my brother (Rab brtan 1944-1999) arranged our marriage. It never occurred to us to have a wedding party because we were too busy struggling to survive.

I gave birth eleven times. One son and two daughters died when they were very young. My other children include two monks, three laypeople, and three daughters. My husband passed away in 2016 from lung cancer. I miss him a lot. After his death, I became a nun.

I didn't go to a nunnery, and I don't wear robes like nuns. I only wear red clothes and cut my hair short like a nun. Importantly, I live by the nuns' rules - no stealing, killing, sexual activities, lying, or proclaiming I am a guru.

I needed to find a *bla ma* and promise him to become a nun face-to-face, so I went to a local *bla ma*, Tshul khrims bzang po.

I forgot to mention that after my husband's death, I stopped eating *bshas sha* 'meat from butchered animals'. Now I only eat *shi sha* 'meat from animals not killed for human consumption'. My husband killed many livestock for our family. I stopped eating *bshas sha* to reduce his sinful deeds [killing livestock].

As I grew older, I accumulated a necklace that was about twenty small coral pieces, two turquoise, and four amber pieces. My family once decided to go to Lha sa, but we didn't have enough money, so my husband and I sold my amber and used that money to travel to Lha sa.

Later, as my children got older, some married and had their own families. Even my grandchildren went to school. I had fewer family responsibilities and had an opportunity to live near the local monastery [Stag lung], so my husband and I built an adobe house here and attended winter religious teachings. I gave all my ornaments to the *bla ma* who gave religious teachings. It was good to offer my ornaments to my *bla ma* rather than sell them or give them to my children. My family members gave me most of my ornaments. Now, most of them have passed away. Offering my ornaments to my *bla ma* will help those who have passed away. I didn't waste my ornaments. Now, my most precious thing is this prayer wheel that my husband also cherished.

¹ See <https://bit.ly/3BmCw1q> 29 July 2022 for more on this mantra.

² Here and elsewhere I've used ?? to indicate an uncertain date.

I don't know who will keep this prayer wheel after I pass away. My mother-in-law, Sher mtsho (1901-1983), spun this prayer wheel so often that she wore out many coins. Let me now explain why there are coins on the prayer wheels. A yak horn washer is under the base of the prayer wheel. A metal coin with a hole through the center is placed on top of a metal washer above the handle's center. When rotated, the yak horn washer and the drum spin simultaneously while the coin washer does not rotate, so the coin washer wears out. The number of worn-out coins you accumulate shows how often you spin the prayer wheel. We lost many of those coins, but I still keep ten.

I believe this prayer wheel is more than 200 years old. One summer morning in the late 1950s, Myang lu and his mates were herding and found a wooden box. Hoping it would be full of treasures, they excitedly opened it. To their disappointment, the box contained only old scriptures and a prayer wheel. At that time, having religious articles or practicing religious activities was forbidden. Anyway, Myang lu surreptitiously put the prayer wheel inside his sheepskin robe and the handle inside his right sleeve. His mates ignored the wooden box since it had no treasures.

Myang lu took the prayer wheel to his home and gave it to his devout mother, who valued it. She turned this prayer wheel countless times and wore out many coins.

I didn't spin this prayer wheel very much when I was younger because I was busy with house chores, herding, taking care of children, and other daily activities. As a woman, you can imagine I had a lot of work to do. A woman is judged on how much work she does. Spending a lot of time spinning a prayer wheel is not what a good young woman should do.

I restored the prayer wheel last year [2021]. My brother (Phur ba, b. 1954) recommended a local metalsmith who made a new copper cover (top: *gnam 'khor lo rtse dgu*, bottom: *sa pad+ma 'dab brgyad*). The original prayer wheel had a red leather cover. The handle is the same. The smith also made silver *sked thag* 'bands' for the center of the prayer wheel. The charge for such a new prayer wheel cover was ~2,600 RMB. However, because of the good relationship between Phur ba and the metal smith, I paid 1,300 RMB.

The *'khor rdo* consists of a small copper piece, ten worn coins, and an artificial turquoise I bought in Lha sa in 2020.

Phyogs las nam rgyal opened my prayer wheel and identified the scripture inside as *Thar mdo*.¹

Ri yongs dga' Idan was sent by Dga' Idan Monastery to our community in the 1950s from Lha sa. He was well-known, sometimes gave religious teachings, and emphasized belief in Buddhism as the most important thing. It will diminish your suffering, and you will be enlightened before or after your death. We believe this prayer wheel belonged to him. Many elders who saw this prayer wheel said it was a *rag khrom 'khor lo*, a term commonly used when I was young. An old monk who visited my home when I was in my forties told me that people turn *rags khrom 'khor lo* prayer wheels during the day and 'dre 'ghosts' turn them at night.

I don't know how much it would bring if I sold it. Nobody has asked to buy it, and I've never said I would sell it or give it away. Continuing to turn this prayer wheel protects against *gdon bgegs* 'evil spirits'. I want to keep this prayer wheel with me forever. As I mentioned, I had other valuable ornaments, but those ornaments are nothing compared to this prayer wheel. I now have no interest in ornaments. This prayer wheel is everything to me. I feel peaceful when I turn it. I worried that I would lose or damage the ornaments I once wore. They brought nothing good, only worry. That is one reason I offered them to my *bla ma*. When I die, the Lord of Death won't value my ornaments.

PART TWO: *SENG GDONG SRUNG BZLOG 'KHOR LO*

Part Two describes Don skyid's family's *seng gdong srung bzlog 'khor lo* 'prayer wheel' and how her family got it. It also explains when and how they spin the 'khor lo.

¹ See <https://bit.ly/3vncTtH> 28 July 2022 for examples of *Thar mdo*.

FIG 8a. Don skyid's family's *seng gdong srung bzlog 'khor lo* (12 February 2023, 'Jam dbyangs skyabs).

FIG 8b. The *seng gdong srung bzlog 'khor lo* (6) is comprised of multiple circular papers of *seng gdong gzungs sngags* 'magic sentences of *seng gdong*'¹ within four bamboo crosses (4), never leaves Don skyid's home, is kept within the black fabric bag (1) when it is not rotated, and it is stored in a lower place in the home that is not obvious. A *bshug gu* 'rope' (2) used to close the bag. The *'khor rdo* (5) is a small circular stone in black cloth. A screwdriver handle (3) serves as the detachable handgrip.

The following account provides insight into Tibetan society's multifaceted religious and cultural practices, traditional customs, and beliefs. It underlines the crucial role of local deities and tangible symbols in seeking assistance and safeguarding oneself. The

¹ I was uncertain about the contents of the paper inside the *'khor lo*, a cylindrical container. Instead of opening it to see what was inside, I sought advice from Phyogs las rnam rgyal. He suggested that such *'khor lo* typically contain layers of circular papers with magic phrases of *seng gdong ma* 'lion-headed one'. For more information about magic sentences, see <https://bit.ly/43M7lIK> and <https://bit.ly/3IYBpb7> 7 June 2023. However, Phyogs las rnam rgyal was unsure of the specific contents. It is worth noting that Chos lo crafted the *'khor lo* and Don skyid and other family members have limited knowledge about it.

significance of incense offerings as a cultural practice and the potential repercussions of disregarding this tradition are highlighted. The account also sheds light on the influential role of *gto bla* and *bla ma* in guiding and providing divination to local people.

My family lost a lot of livestock in 2002 and 2003. Thieves stole many yaks, and wolves killed many sheep. We were worried, so my husband got this '*khor lo*' from a *gto bla*.¹ It is a *seng gdong srung bzlog 'khor lo*. The *gto bla* suggested my husband make this *seng gdong srung bzlog 'khor lo* and spin it counterclockwise. He emphasized this *seng gdong srung bzlog 'khor lo* should never be higher than your knees. We didn't find it helpful, so Phyogs las rnam rgyal visited Phyang 'tshal a lags (b. 1971) and asked him for a *pra pa* 'mirror divination'.² Phyang 'tshal a lags told him our family was not offering incense to a deity with physical embodiments that represent the deity. For example, one of these physical embodiments is a black horse with gray lips, groin, eye edges, and armpits, known as a *rta bra bra* 'gray horse'.³ Another physical embodiment is a dark lance with a black banner called *mdung dar smug po can* 'purple lance carrier'. These physical embodiments symbolize and honor the tribe deity tangibly. Phyang 'tshal a lags refers to my natal home deity, Lcam gyi bra bo, with features Phyang 'tshal a lags described.

As mentioned, the deity venerated in my natal home, Lcam gyi bra bo, is considered a non-Buddhistic deity, as are all the deities in my home community. These deities have the power to assist us in our current life but are incapable of

¹ A *bla ma* who performs rituals to avert misfortune.

² According to Phyogs las rnam rgyal, the mirror divination Bstan pa'i dbang phyug does is actually *gid bra* 'mind divination' because he doesn't use a mirror. Instead, he uses his mind to determine *la nye* 'signs'. Some 'mirror divination' diviners rely on mirrors to see signs by tossing rice on mirrors and looking for signs on the mirrors. People who have pika eyes easily see the signs on the mirror, though they may not be diviners, thanks to their naturally gifted pika eyes. They may see *sha za* 'flesh-eating demons' and *lha mthong 'dre mthong* 'gods and demons'. A mirror diviner who lacks pika eyes may invite a man with pika eyes to look at the mirror and describe what he sees. (I never heard of a mirror divination diviner inviting a woman with pika eyes).

³ Translating the name of the horse into English is not straightforward as it is a common colloquial name used for that type of horse. I am uncertain about the accuracy of the translation.

helping us achieve a better next life. For instance, if we wish to win a horse race, we may offer incense to the deity in the hopes of receiving their aid. Consequently, we do not offer prostrations to the deities as we would *bla ma*, monks, and Buddhas, as these figures have the power to aid us in our current and future lives.

If a family miss offering incense to a deity, it may be considered a lapse in showing proper reverence to the deity. For example, I married and moved to my husband's home place. If my husband's family doesn't offer incense to my natal home deity, misfortune may come to my husband's family, such as livestock stolen by thieves or predation by wolves.

Everything steadily improved once we began offering incense to Lcam gyi bra bo annually.

Lcam gyi bra bo is a local deity of the A bzod Tribe. He has a female deity partner, Lcam gyi bra mo. Each deity has its mountain. A bzod people go there annually to offer incense around the tenth day of the fourth month. If you compare these two mountain deities, the male deity has more people offering incense and respect than the female deity. Locals believe that the male deity is the main deity, so many people don't offer incense to the female deity.

My family lives far from my natal A bzod Tribe, so it is not always convenient for us to make an annual trip to offer incense to the deity. However, we still do so because we believe that neglecting this practice may lead to misfortunes befalling our family again.

A khu bkra phun (1946-2020), a *bla ma* from A bzod Monastery,¹ told me, "If your family finds it inconvenient to make an annual trip to offer incense to the deity, there is an alternative approach. It involves taking stones from the deity's offering incense platform and using them to perform the incense offering ritual at your home."

We continue offering my natal home, A bzod Tribe deity incense annually. My sons take turns going every year. While we don't doubt what A khu bkra phun suggested, we are apprehensive about misfortune befalling our family if we don't visit.

In addition, there is a revered deity known as Spen ma'i g.yu rgyal phyug mo in my husband's home in Spen ma Valley, Khang sar Tribe. This deity is highly regarded, and offering incense is necessary to avoid misfortune. Furthermore, locals are careful not to engage in any behavior that may offend the deity, such as laughing while offering incense on the mountain of Spen ma'i g.yu rgyal phyug mo

¹ For more, see <https://bit.ly/3K1ERmi> 20 February 2023.

or killing animals, particularly wolves, as they are believed to belong to the deity. Any mistreatment of such animals is thought to bring negative consequences.

PART THREE: CHOS MDZAD (B. 1938) AND YI PO (B. 1941) AND THEIR FIVE PRAYER WHEELS

Part Three offers biographical sketches of Chos mdzad (b. 1938) and his wife, Yi po (b. 1941), and provides descriptions of their five prayer wheels: two *thar 'khor*, a *sgrol ma'i 'khor lo*, a *ma Ni'i 'khor lo*, and a *'then 'khor*.

FIG 9. Chos mdzad's right-hand grips a *thar 'khor* (1,2) while his left-hand holds a *ma Ni'i 'khor lo*, in Chos mdzad and Yi po's home near Stag lung Monastery (2022, 'Jam dbyangs skyabs).

This personal narrative is an intimate account of the daily routines, family life, and religious practices of a Tibetan couple named Chos mdzad and Yi po. The couple's beliefs and cultural traditions are deeply rooted in their religious practices, which are a significant part of their lives. Additionally, the narrative delves into

the couple's early life and the gradual acquisition of their five prayer wheels, including two *thar 'khor*, a *sgrol ma'i 'khor lo*, a *ma Ni'i 'khor lo*, and a *'then 'khor*, providing historical and cultural context. This account offers insight into Tibetan culture and traditions through Chos mdzad and Yi po's personal experiences.

My name is Chos mdzad. Yi po is my wife. We married when I was twenty-four, and Yi po was twenty-one. My wife came to my home with her first child, who was about one year old, and then the child suddenly died. We didn't perform a sky burial or water burial. Instead, we held *chod 'og tu 'phangs pa*¹ to protect our future children from *chung sri*² 'infant-demon' attack. We buried the baby under a bridge. It is very important to find a place located under a bridge or road that is auspicious. If not, it is *chod nag la shor ba*.³ If the ritual goes well, future children won't die. However, unfortunately, after we lost my wife's first baby, we couldn't have children. We assumed the ritual didn't go well - the bridge burial site wasn't auspicious. We then adopted Mi 'gyur (b. 1983), who later married Phyug mtsho (b. 1985). They have two children, Sher po (b. 2005), a student, and 'Jigs phun (b. 2015), a monk. We started to live in Mtha' ba Community in 2005. We are raising both children while their parents are busy herding our livestock.

My feet started to become uncomfortable when I was in my fifties and gradually became very painful. In 2019, I was affected by gout. I consulted Chinese and Tibetan doctors, but they couldn't cure my gout completely. I rarely circumambulate or do prostrations because of my poor knees and feet. I stay home most of the time, spin my prayer wheels, and chant scriptures and mantras. My wife's feet and knees are in good shape compared to mine. She circumambulates and prostrates. I admire her. She also cooks for us and does the dishes when Sher po attends the local Tibetan Middle School where she must board. Sher po spends her vacations with us and helps us cook, wash dishes, and do house chores. She is quite handy. We appreciate her. 'Jigs phun is young, and we don't expect him to help us cook and do house chores.

¹ This is a local ritual. If the first child dies, the family may worry that they have become a *chung sri* and hold the ritual in the hopes of preventing the misfortune of future children dying.

² For more on *chung sri*, see <https://bit.ly/3tosF5U> and <https://bit.ly/3zU2Qio> 12 November 2022.

³ A characteristic of *chod nag la shor ba* is that if the ritual '*chod 'og tu 'phangs pa*' is done in a wrong place, it cuts off the *skye rgyud* 'family line'.

FIG 10. *Thar 'khor* (1,2) in Chos mdzad and Yi po's home near Stag lung Monastery (2022, 'Jam dbyangs skyabs).

I found this *thar 'khor* in the river in Lung ring 'Long Valley' in 1959 in early winter when the river was ice-covered. I was twenty-one. When I found it, it was without '*khor rdo*, '*khor yo*, and *tog*. I took it home and dried it.

We were not allowed to spin prayer wheels and publicly engage in religious activities for years. Blo brtan "Rgya rag," a monk, helped me change the original leather *thar 'khor* cover for a new leather cover. He herded horses for Sgo mang Monastery. Although he was a monk, he didn't wear a monastic robe. He wore a yellow Tibetan robe. Hwar ba a lags'¹ (b. 1948)

teacher was important to my family and our neighbor families. At that time, if we needed to chant something, finding a monk or a *bla ma* who would chant was very difficult. They were not allowed to do such a thing. However, we secretly asked him to chant. Whenever he agreed to chant, those responsible had to promise they wouldn't tell anybody.

As I mentioned, when I first found the *thar 'khor*, it didn't have a '*khor lo 'i yu ba* 'handle' so I made a juniper handle and a *tog* of silver. My mother (1913-??) found a silver '*khor rdo* before I found my *thar 'khor*. When she went to Smin thang to grind barley, she found this silver '*khor rdo* in a piece of felt. She was unsure what it was when she first saw it on the ground, but picking it up, she immediately knew it was a silver '*khor rdo*, which I then used. A piece of small bamboo is under my *thar 'khor*. Earlier, it was a *mdzo* horn. I had a riding *mdzo* with a nose ring that I rode when I herded livestock. After it died, I used its horn as a '*khor lte*.³

Later, Kho lo (Khya bza') told us that *thar 'khor* was her family's, emphasizing it belonged to Dkar dbang's mother. I don't know how leader Dkar

¹ For more on Hwar ba a lags, see <https://bit.ly/3fFZdFo> 12 November 2022.

² <https://bit.ly/3UmXCmM> November 2022.

³ <https://bit.ly/3zMZ4qG> 7 November 2022.

dbang's family got this *thar 'khor*.

Unlike today, prayer wheels were quite rare at that time.

We lost the silver *tog* the day we moved from the summer pasture to the winter pasture by pack yaks. I thought we might have lost it in our *mtsher shul* 'remains of a seasonal dwelling site', so I returned to search for it. We never found it, so I used another prayer wheel's *tog*.

My mother wore out twenty coins in spinning my *thar 'khor*. You can see some of the worn-out coins with the *'khor rdo*.

The cover of this prayer wheel is original. We didn't change it.

As you can see, another prayer wheel is on top of my *thar 'khor*. It is also a *thar 'khor*(2). A Bsu ba Monastery¹ monk gave it to me. My duty was herding my family's sheep, and occasionally, I needed to kill one or two a year for meat. When the monk gave me this *thar 'khor*, he said, "You kill a lot of livestock. That is a sin. Please spin this *thar 'khor* to reduce your sin."

When the monk gave me this *thar 'khor*, it had *'khor yo*, *'khor rdo*, and everything a prayer wheel needs to have. Carrying two prayer wheels while herding was inconvenient, so I used only one *'khor yo*.

The top of the *thar 'khor* the monk gave has a cloth covering. My wife and I planned to change it to a leather one, but our eyesight is not very good now so we couldn't make a leather cover.

FIG 11. Parts of the *thar 'khor* (1, 2):

- | | |
|--------------------------------|--|
| 1. <i>sked thag</i> 'band' | 2. <i>'khor rdo</i> 'prayer wheel stone' |
| 3. <i>dong tse</i> 'coins' | 4. <i>'khor lte</i> 'rotating sleeve' |
| 5. <i>dung dkar</i> 'seashell' | 6. <i>'khor lo'i yu ba</i> 'handle' |
| 7. <i>thar 'khor</i> (2) | 8. <i>tog</i> 'top' |

¹ <https://bit.ly/3DKMRE5> 7 November 2022.

Our second prayer wheel is a *sgrol ma'i 'khor lo* (3), which I found when I was twenty-nine. Rnam grol gave me a red leather cover for it. Rnam grol was Bde sgrol's brother, who passed away long ago. Rnam grol got it from a D+hHphu Monastery¹ *bla ma*. He didn't identify the *bla ma* who gave it to him.

Long story short, I was herding my sheep on the mountain one winter day, and as was my habit, I brought the *sgrol ma'i 'khor lo* with me. Every time I went herding, I took it and rotated it. When I noticed my sheep had scattered, I put my felt hat on the ground, put my *sgrol ma'i 'khor lo* on that, and went to drive the sheep back. I couldn't find my *sgrol ma'i 'khor lo* when I returned. Whoever found it must have

thought it was funny because I had left it on a hat on the ground. That's all I have to say about my second prayer wheel, the *sgrol ma'i 'khor lo*.

FIG 12. The *ma Ni'i 'khor lo* in Chos mdzad and Yi po's home near Stag lung Monastery (2022, 'Jam dbyangs skyabs).

This *ma Ni'i 'khor lo* is our third prayer wheel, which we call a silver prayer wheel because of its silver cover.

A monk, A khu blos tshul, gave me a *ma Ni'i* scripture, which I put inside the silver cover. He used to be a *mkhan po*² in Rdo grub chen Monastery. Later A khu blos tshul and his family moved near Rnga ba and settled because one of his brothers (Rong dpal) had a dispute in their home community. A khu blos tshul's family was very poor, and the King of Rme'u³ asked Rong dpal to join an old childless couple. The King arranged such situations, asking young, healthy people to help old people who had enough resources to support themselves but were physically weak and unhealthy. The King ensured the young people were willing to help and care for them until they passed away. The young people were then allowed to own their property.

A khu blos tshul was in his fifties when I met him. He had many old religious

¹ <https://bit.ly/3DK6b5K> 22 September 2022.

² <https://bit.ly/3WzVXMn> 4 November 2022.

³ <https://bit.ly/3U6DaXd> 4 November 2022.

items, such as small stupas, *rdo rje*,¹ and other items. I don't know what happened to them. Maybe A khu blos tshul offered them to monasteries.

A khu blos tshul used to go to every Khang sar Community household and chant scriptures. He helped our community a lot by chanting for families who needed it. For example, if someone passed away, he secretly went to that family and chanted. Chanting was illegal then, and everyone was aware of the consequences.

A khu blos tshul was a diviner and a *rtsis pa* 'soothsayer'. I don't know if there is a current reincarnation. His family might know that.

A tall monk helped to make the silver cover of my *ma Ni'i 'khor lo*. We went to Rnga ba, where a metalsmith, Ri lo, in Dbon pa Village, made the silver cover for our *ma Ni'i 'khor lo*.

FIG 13. *Ma Ni'i 'khor lo* parts in Chos mdzad and Yi po's home near Stag lung Monastery (2022, 'Jam dbyangs skyabs):

1. '*khor lte* 'rotating sleeve'
2. *sked thag* 'band'
3. '*khor rdo* 'prayer wheel stone'
4. *dong tse* 'coins'
5. *tog* 'top'
6. '*khor lo'i yu ba* 'handle'

FIG 14. The '*then 'khor* 'pulled prayer wheel' (5) in Chos mdzad and Yi po's home near Stag lung Monastery (2022, 'Jam dbyangs skyabs).

¹ <https://bit.ly/3zHLm8j> 4 November 2022.

² <https://bit.ly/3WsMsi2> 4 November 2022.

This *'then 'khor* is our fourth prayer wheel. It doesn't have a *'khor rdo*. It has a rope under the actual prayer wheel that we pull to spin it. This *bka' 'gyur 'khor lo*¹ and Sher po are the same age. In 2004, Stag lung dgon bought many prayer wheels for the monastery (not to sell). My wife and I wanted one and asked Thub chos, my nephew, to help us. We assured we would pay for it. He agreed to help. We didn't pay cash. My wife, Yi po, went to our herding place during summer to help Mi 'gyur and Phyug mtsho. Meanwhile, she

collected three kilograms of dried fritillary, sold it, and paid for the *'then 'khor*.

Nowadays, people have many prayer wheels and don't worry about not affording them. Prayer wheels are everywhere. It's not like when I was young when getting a prayer wheel was not easy. Now you just need passion for spinning prayer wheels. I have gout and can't walk very far. I am becoming bedridden. My wife is my primary assistant. Gout doesn't allow me to go outside our yard, but it is OK in a way because I can do daily religious recitations and spin our several prayer wheels.

I am eighty-four, which is a perfect time to die. I'm still not completely disabled. I will not cause my wife and family more trouble if I die now. Eighty-four years is a long time.

¹ <https://bit.ly/3Ui4JwM> 4 November 2022.

FIG 15. Parts of the 'then 'khor in Chos mdzad and Yi po's home near Stag lung Monastery (2022, 'Jam dbyangs skyabs):

1. *srog shing* 'main beam'
2. *steng lte* 'top rotating sleeve'
3. *gdugs* 'top parasol'
4. *phur ma* 'a folded silk'
5. '*khor thag* 'belt'
6. '*then lung* 'pull rope'
7. '*og lte* 'bottom rotating sleeve'

PART FOUR: BDE SGROL'S (B. 1947) *YIG BRGYA'I 'KHOR LO*

Part Four describes the life of Bde sgrol (b. 1947, also known as Zha ye), and her *yig brgya'i 'khor lo*, its history, and its value to her, providing insights into traditional Tibetan nomadic life and customs. The narrative describes cultural and historical details, including the various tribes, the livestock they raised, and the challenges they faced.

It offers a glimpse into the life of a woman who lived through different periods of Tibetan history and saw the introduction of new ways of life. Zha ye's life story reflects how Tibetan nomads' traditional way of life has changed over time and how modernization has impacted traditional cultural practices.

The account highlights the importance of family, community, and spirituality in traditional Tibetan culture.

My name is Zha ye, which means 'baby'. It is my real name, but people stopped calling me that after I moved to Mtha' ba Community in 2006. They called me Bde sgrol. I don't know who gave me that name. In 2009, I went to Tshul khriims bzang po and became a *dge bsnyen ma*'lay female votary of Buddha'. He gave me a new name - Byang chub sgrol ma - because I took *dge bsnyen*¹ vows. I like that name and hoped I would be called that, but people continued to call me Bde sgrol.

My father, Chos lo, and mother, Khug skyid, passed away in their eighties. They had twelve children. I was the youngest. I married Dkon bsam (1953-~2005) when I was nineteen. We had eight children. Three died when they were infants. The others are Rig pe (b. 1967), Bde mo (b. 1971), Tshe dbang mtsho (b. 1974), Lha mtsho (b. 1977), and Skal pe (b. 1985).

I herded yaks, sheep, and horses. I am thankful for my livestock. My family would have died in the famine without them.

My husband and I herded 1,000 sheep and one hundred horses for the gongshe 'commune' in Gsa' khog Valley for about eighteen years. We married in Gsa' khog while we were herding there. Dkon bsam's family was very poor. We only had three female yaks. We had enough food and clothes to wear, thanks to our beloved yaks. We survived.

While in Gsa' khog, my husband's parents persuaded us to come to the

¹ For more on *dge bsnyen*, see <https://bit.ly/3IXPyWJ> 23 February 2023.

Gsa' skor Tribe and live near them. So, one day we went to the Gsa' skor Tribe. Unfortunately, the Gsa' skor Tribe leader rejected us. We didn't know why. Maybe it was because we married outside of the tribe. We then moved to the neighboring Dug bza' Tribe. I regretted leaving Gsa' skor after so many years there. I love the Gsa' khog mountains, grasslands, and life there. I fondly remember them.

Gsa' khog and Dbal ban border each other. In Gsa' khog, Dkon bsam went to Dbal ban and bought a *mdzo stag stag dung rked can*¹ from Nyal kho, a monk. We gave Nyal kho a female yak and a sheep for it. I liked that *mdzo* a lot. The first time we brought the *mdzo* to our pasture, big strong male yaks bullied him, especially at night when we drove all the yaks into the yak enclosure. So, I tied him inside our yak hair tent to protect him from the other yaks. Gradually, the yaks adopted him as one of their members. He had offspring.² I never considered selling him or his offspring. Now, I live in Mtha' ba Community, where I'm not much involved in herding. My daughter, Rig pe, and her husband care for everything related to herding. Unlike me, they are not fond of *mdzo*. Now we have a few old *mdzo*. When I was young, we considered the number of livestock and cared about their color and beauty. If a family had one or two beautiful *mdzo*, we admired that family and hoped our females would have their offspring.

Today is different, with people herding yaks for cash. When I was young, we herded livestock for food, clothing, and housing. We milked yaks in the morning, afternoon, and evening. Children were busy chasing calves to keep them separate from their mothers. We were afraid the calves would nurse their mothers, leaving no milk. Milk is everything when you think of our food - butter, cheese, and milk tea. In terms of clothing, we made leather shoes, sheepskin robes, lambskin robes, and felt for raincoats. Even our housing is related to livestock. Yak hair tents are made of yak hair. Oh, I nearly forgot, we got meat from the livestock we slaughtered or other predators such as wolves killed or that died from natural causes. In contrast, now people sell yaks and buy things. Making things by themselves is not something people do today.

FIG 16. Bde sgrol holds a *yig brgya'i 'khor lo* in her right hand at Don skyid's home near Stag lung Monastery (2023, 'Jam dbyangs

¹ A *mdzo* is the male offspring of a yak mother and bull (cattle). *Stag stag dung rked can* may be translated as 'tiger-colored with a big white spot on the belly'.

² *Mdzo* are generally thought to be sterile, however, Zha ye reported this *mdzo* had offspring.

skyabs).

Dus po was my husband's pious aunt. Her husband was Ban so, from Smin thang. They had no children. Dus po was the commune cook when my husband and I herded livestock in Gsa' khog. Dus po and her husband stayed in Smin thang, but Dus po decided to leave her husband and return to her natal home in Khang sar several years before she passed away.

Dus po was fond of visiting our home and once spent the night at our home and the next day returned to her home. She forgot to take the *yig brgya'i 'khor lo*, so we kept it. This was several years before she passed away. I don't know how she got the *yig brgya'i 'khor lo*. Dkon bsam said the prayer wheel was a *yig brgya'i*

'*khor lo*. I didn't open it to check. I believed Dkon bsam.

To continue my story about the *yig brgya'i 'khor lo*. One morning in 2017, I ate a simple breakfast. My neighbor's family was holding a funeral and relatives and friends of the family and neighbors had come to help the family. I am old, and there was nothing I could help with, so I grabbed my prayer beads, chanted *ma Ni*, and circumambulated.

I felt a bit hungry at noon and returned home. When I got near, I saw smoke above my house. My house was on fire! Luckily the fire didn't destroy my house completely. My neighbor's family had noticed the fire and extinguished it.

I learned that my cat started the fire by turning over a butter lamp before the Buddha images. Another prayer wheel, a *ma Ni'i 'khor lo*, my bed, and my window frames were also burned. I put my *ma Ni'i 'khor lo* on top of a *rde'u 'bum* 'a mound of pebbles'.

The fire also burnt the handle of the *yig brgya'i 'khor lo*, the '*khor rdo*, and parts of the '*khor lo*. When Don bkra, the husband of my daughter, Lha mtsho, visited me, he noticed my burnt *yig brgya'i 'khor lo*, offered to fix it, took it to the herding place, and several weeks later he returned it. He is skilled at sewing and making things. He made a handle using the radius bone of his family's recently dead mare. The top and bottom of the handle are decorated with silver. That mare was important to his family because most of their horses are her offspring. My son-in-law told me that the mare died painfully, unable to eat or drink because she was old.

FIG 17. 'Jam dbyangs skyabs holds Bde sgrol's *yig brgya'i 'khor lo* in Don skyid's home near Stag lung Monastery (2023, 'Jam dbyangs skyabs).

PART FIVE: RELIGIOUS ITEMS DON SKYID WEARS AROUND HER NECK

Part Five features religious items Don skyid wears around her neck. The background and meaning are described for each item. These items include *sgar gyi phreng ba*, *bcu tshad*, *btags grol*, *srung 'khor*, *nag po dgu sbyor*, and *bye lcags*. Don skyid's shares her personal experiences with religion and its role in her life, including practices and beliefs. She describes in detail the meaning and significance of the religious items she wears and includes how a monk helped her granddaughter recover from an illness.

Don skyid is not alone in her religious practices. Others in her community share similar beliefs and engage in comparable rituals. Her faith is a personal matter deeply intertwined with her family and community. Her story provides insight into how religion can play a meaningful role in people's lives and unites communities.

FIG 18. Items Don skyid wears: (1) *sgar gyi phreng ba*, (2) *bcu tshad*, (3) *btags grol*,¹ (4) *srung 'khor*, (5) *nag po dgu sbyor*, and (6) *bye lcags*² (2022, 'Jam dbyangs skyabs).

¹ <https://bit.ly/3PHBWPX> 29 July 2022.

² Don skyid used this term that literally translates as 'ten-million metal'. When chanting scripture or mantra, such as *ma Ni*, ten-million times, the chanter should count one bead from their prayer beads, indicating they have chanted *ma Ni* ten-million times.

- (1) *Sgar gyi phreng ba*. I chanted *oM a mi de wa hrIH*¹ 10,000 times, so I qualified to receive this for free from Bla rung sgar Monastery. Hair from Chos rje yid bzhin nor bu is in the beads.
- (2) *Bcu tshad*. When I chant, I use these two *bcu tshad* to count the number of times I chant. Each *bcu tshad* has ten beads, so if I chant *ma Ni* a hundred times, I count this by separating one bead from the other nine beads. Counting ten beads means I have chanted *ma Ni* 1,000 times, and I then count one bead from the other *bcu tshad*. One bead from one of the *bcu tshad* represents a hundred, and one bead from the other *bcu tshad* represents a thousand.
- (3) *Btags grol* 'liberation by wearing'. A khu stag lha (1945-2018) gave it to me fifteen years ago. When I asked my husband if he wanted it, he said, "No, you keep it. A khu stag lha gave it to you." After a few years, the string broke, and I couldn't identify the top and bottom, so I asked my oldest monk son to open it because there were Tibetan letters inside, and some *srung 'khor'* amulets' have Buddha images. He then told me which end was the top, so I made the new cover you see in the photo. The *btags grol* is very important to me because A khu stag lha gave it to me, and he was important to me.

One time, he saved the life of G.yang res, my granddaughter:

G.yang res (b. 1990) was suddenly very sick, so her mother, Rtse pe (b. 1965), and I rode our horses to see A khu stag lha in the afternoon. It wasn't easy to go to the local hospital and consult doctors there because we couldn't communicate with them well [we couldn't speak Chinese], and if you wanted or needed to go to the local hospital, you had to have a good connection. We also didn't have much money and couldn't afford medicine. We were very worried about G.yang res. She couldn't open her eyes. A khu stag lha was a doctor and a *bla ma*. When we approached his place, he was coming out of his house, seemingly leaving. I knew him well. He was from my natal home [Sog ru], so I pleaded, "You must save my granddaughter."

He looked at my granddaughter and said, "I know you are very worried about her. She looks very sick, so I am afraid I cannot help you."

But then we went into his house, and he told his assistant to give my granddaughter a *ril bu* 'pill', which we put in her mouth as A khu stag lha

¹ *oM* 'I invoke the universal sound', *a mi* 'limitless light', *de wa*, 'Buddha nature', and *hrIH* 'with self-respect'. See <https://bit.ly/3S5hZ7z> 29 July 2022 for more.

chanted *gcod* 'cut off'.¹ When he finished chanting, he said, "Yes, we did it. I promise she'll be fine. Now you can go home. Maybe it's also good if you see a doctor and she gets an IV."

After the chanting, G.yang res looked better. We thanked him and left. She didn't get an IV because I thought an IV was unnecessary. Instead, we went directly to visit Phyogs las rnam rgyal, who had a small room in the monastery. We spent the night there.

The next day, we rode back to our pasture. When we arrived, my husband told me that our dog, Ser lo 'Yellow', had died the previous night. I asked, "What happened? How did Ser lo die?"

This morning, I was going to feed him. Snow was on the ground, and I could tell Ser lo was in his kennel because there were no footprints. I called him several times, but he didn't come out, so I went to the kennel and found he was dead. He didn't even move. His mouth was under his tail.

My husband traded a sheep for Ser lo with a relative in Rnga ba. Ser lo was aggressive, and we didn't like him. Before the birth of G.yang res, my oldest son and his wife had a son who had died five days after his birth. The child was my oldest son's first child, and we worried. So, we invited Khya dge a legs to our home and asked him to divine the cause of the child's death. He divined and said Ser lo was a *gdon* 'malevolent influence,' but he also emphasized that we should not get rid of Ser lo because that might bring more bad fortune. So, we did religious rituals to prevent misfortune.

I believe G.yang res got sick because of Ser lo. A khu stag lha chanted *Gcod*, and that exorcised the malevolent influence. Therefore, no other of my oldest son's children got seriously ill.

(4) *Srung 'khor*. I don't know what's inside this amulet, so I don't know what kind of amulet it is. Anyway, my relatives from Sog ru once visited, gave it to me, saying, "Many people in our home place have this amulet." They got it from Bla rung sgar Monastery.

¹ For more on *gcod* 'Tibetan Buddhist rite', see <https://bit.ly/3S9vMtA> 29 July 2022.

- (5) *Nag po dgu sbyor*. I got this Tibetan pill, a *nag po dgu sbyor* 'black-9',¹ from Stag lung Monastery, which gave a black-9 to every person in each local community to prevent COVID. I heard people say that old people, pregnant women, and infants should not always wear it because of its side effects. The proper way is to smell it a few times a day. However, I always take it with me because I sometimes forget to smell it.
- (6) *Bye lcags* 'ten-million-metal'. I never use this. I have it with my prayer beads. For example, if I chant *ma Ni* ten million times, I should count one bead from my prayer beads and use *bye lcags* as a marker. To be honest, I haven't chanted that number.

Don skyid wears other items she could not provide background for, e.g., a round medallion featuring the bust of a religious person (whose name/title she could not remember), a red bead, and *mdud pa* 'protection cords'.

PART SIX: DON SKYID'S FAMILY'S YAK HAIR TENTS (*SBRA LEB* AND *NAG TSHANG*)² AND HOUSES

Part Six describes the yak hair tents that Don skyid's family once used, including a *sbra leb* and *nag tshang*. She also gives a brief history of her family's houses. This account sheds light on the significance of self-sufficiency and the traditional lifestyle in the region. It narrates how a family inherited their tents, a *sbra leb*, and a *nag tshang*, and how these items were passed down from generation to generation, which is particularly intriguing. Moreover, the account showcases various types of yak hair tents, each with its purpose and design, emphasizing their constant renewal and maintenance requirements, demonstrating the resourcefulness and adaptability of those who relied on these tents.

The narrator also mentions an uncomplicated exchange system between locals and those from Rnga ba, enabling the family to prosper without the conveniences of modern life. Overall, the

¹ For more on *nag po dgu sbyor*, see <https://bit.ly/3zkebxXc> 29 July 2022.

² The *sbra leb* 'flat tent' and *nag tshang* 'black housing' are both used by a family and differ in size, with the former larger than the latter.

account offers a glimpse into a lifestyle very different from contemporary living. It portrays how the narrator's community depended on their herds and traditional knowledge to survive and how the yak hair tent played a crucial role in their existence.

Sbra leb and *Nag tshang*

My family is fortunate to own two types of yak hair tents: a *sbra leb* and a *nag tshang*. These are just two examples of the many types of yak hair tents, including the *nyal sbra* 'sleeping tent' often pitched near the main tent or sheep enclosure, the *klad nag* 'black top' which, because it is predominantly canvas, some argue it is not a true yak hair tent, and the *lug ba 'i sbra* 'shepherd tent' which is easy to assemble and used for short-term sheep grazing.

Another is the *tshogs sbra* 'assembly tent' used specifically for Buddhist services. Growing up in the Khang sar and Sog ru tribes, I recall each tribe had its own monastery tent that followed the tribe wherever they went. As a woman who primarily stayed at home, my knowledge of the various types of yak hair tents is limited. I humbly acknowledge I do not know if you ask me how many different types of yak hair tents Tibetans typically use.

During my youth, it was not just women who stayed at home but men as well. We were occupied with herding livestock, making such clothing as sheepskin robes and leather boots, and renewing our yak hair tents. These tents were unlike the canvas ones that can be easily purchased in markets today for 700 to 2,000 RMB and then replaced a few years later. I am not exaggerating when I say that money was not highly valued in our society in the past. We were self-sufficient and, aside from barley, needed little from the outside world. Since we were nomads, we did not cultivate vegetables, relying on our herds and dairy products.

Barley was a staple of our diet. On certain occasions, such as during the New Year or when a family member passed away, we invited monks and *bla ma* to chant *zhe dgu* (a forty-nine-day ritual performed after a person's death) or *shi tshigs* (a yearly ritual performed after a person's death). During these rituals, we offered *phye* 'wheat flour', *bye ma ka ra* 'granulated sugar', and salt. The head of the family (a man unless there were no adult men) would go to Rnga ba, where grains, vegetables, and fruits were cultivated to purchase these items. People from Rnga ba sometimes came to our place to exchange barley, apples, and potatoes for butter, cheese, yak skins, and sheepskins. The exchange between local people here and the Rnga ba people was a simple, efficient system that

allowed us to thrive without the luxuries of the modern world.

As a youth, I recall even men didn't have many opportunities to leave home. We were busy with what I've mentioned. Unlike modern white tents readily available for purchase, our tents required frequent maintenance and renewal.

Now, I want to tell you a story that illustrates how yak hair tents did not remain the same. They were constantly changing:

Many years ago, a son and his mother lived together. One time they quarreled. The mother was so angry she said to her son, "Unreliable. Don't live with me anymore. Leave my yak hair tent! Never come back! I don't have such a bad son like you!"

The son responded, "Your original tent is gone. I have frequently helped repair this tent. It's also partly mine."

The son was right. A yak hair tent never remained the same, even for one year. Every year people do *sbra gso*.¹

FIG 19. Don skyid's family's yak hair tent (9 August 2022, 'Jam dbyangs skyabs).

¹ *Sbra gso* 'bringing up a tent'. Once a year, old cloth is removed from the edge near the ground and new cloth is added to the edge of the yak hair tent top.

My family's *sbra leb* was used for at least four generations. My husband's father's father originally owned it. At that time, people said, "*Bu rgyus sbra ring tshang gi sbra red rgya shar ba 'bab sa red.*"¹

Dme sman or Sman lha² married Dme shul bza' shar ba, whose family was wealthy. When she married Sman lha, her family gave them this tent. They had four children, Bde skyid, Blo ldan, 'Be tho, and Tho skyid. Sman lha and his wife, Dme shul bza' shar ba, gave the *sbra leb* to 'Be tho, who married Khra bza' sher mtsho. My husband's parents gave us the *sbra leb*. That was how we came to own it. It now belongs to my oldest son, Tshe brtan.

My eleven children were all born in our *sbra leb*. My family lived in a yak hair tent until 1989, the year of the tenth PaN chen rin po che's death. I remember that. It was the year my family had our first adobe house in Mtha' ba Community near Stag lung dgon ka dag spros bral gling. Many of our friends and relatives from Rnga ba helped us build that house. They were good at tamping adobe walls and building houses. Building an adobe house requires a lot of wood. In autumn, we sell livestock. So, my oldest son Tshe brtan went to the local County Town to sell some livestock. He took the money and went to Rnga ba and bought a big Dongfeng truck of wood for about 3,000 RMB, which was a lot at that time. A neighbor had wood boards, and we had timbers. We exchanged some with each other. I made a mud hearth in our first adobe house.

FIG 20. Don skyid's family's *sbra leb*, two large leather sacks, and four sacks in Don skyid's home in Mtha' ba Community. The man is Tshe brtan (9 August 2022, 'Jam dbyangs skyabs).

1. My family's *sbra leb* is folded and fastened with *rtsid thag* 'yak hair rope'. Nowadays, we keep our *sbra leb* stored. We don't pitch it anymore. However, my children and I share great memories of living in the *sbra leb*. The time we spent in the *sbra leb* was not perfect. For example, we worried about leaks and other issues when it rained. Nevertheless, I have never forgotten that my husband and I raised our children in our *sbra leb*. It was our home.

2. My husband and I made those two big leather sacks. Nowadays, various types of sacks are available, and people don't use leather sacks anymore.

¹ This might be explained in this way: Bu rgyus' (a person/family) long yak hair tent where Western Chinese (soldiers and merchants) stayed. "West" refers to such places as Zi ling (Xining).

² He was called these two names interchangeably.

3. We bought four white sacks for my oldest son's third daughter's wedding in 2022.

Later, our first adobe house walls disintegrated, so we built another house in 2009 in the same place. That's where I live now.

My family also built a house in Stag lung dgon ka dag spros bral gling in 2002 for my two monk sons. That was the most expensive house my family built. We bought juniper timber from Pad+ma County. Juniper is more expensive than other timber. We built a house in Stag lung dgon ka dag spros bral gling and another in the Mtha' ba Community. Every year our local monastery holds a *dbyar gnas*¹ 'summer retreat'. This is a time women are not allowed to enter the monastery and monks are not allowed to leave the monastery, so it is important to have two houses - one in the monastery and another in Mtha' ba Community.

PART SEVEN: TSHE BRTAN'S ORNAMENTS

Part Seven concerns Tshe brtan's life and the background of his inherited precious *mchong* 'agate' that he wears around his neck. Readers are given a glimpse into the life of Tshe brtan, a man from Gcig sgril County who has taken over as the head of his family after his father's death. The section illustrates his strong sense of responsibility towards his large family and his concerns regarding

¹ For more, see <https://bit.ly/3YPDBaT> 20 February 2023.

their well-being, health, and overall quality of life. We learn of Tshe brtan's relationship with his father, who taught him self-reliance and fortitude, and bequeathed to him the family's cherished *mchong*, which Tshe brtan reveres as a symbol of prosperity and good fortune.

This account offers insight into the importance of family and tradition in Tshe brtan's life as he faces various challenges, such as the loss of his first son and worries about the future of his sisters and daughters. Nevertheless, he remains devoted to his role as the head of the family and preserving his family's heritage. The significance of material possessions, such as the *mchong*, as markers of cultural identity and family history are emphasized. Through Tshe brtan's experiences, readers are invited to reflect on the role of family, tradition, and material objects in their lives and the values they hold in high esteem:

My name is Tshe brtan. My parents are Don skyid and Bsod dar. I am the oldest of my three sisters and four brothers. I am married to Rtse pe (b. 1965). We have three daughters, G.yang res, Dpal Idan skyid (b. 1994) G.yang phyug (b. 1995), and one son, Ye shes bzang po, b. 1996). Our first child passed away several days after his birth.

We sent Ye shes bzang po to Stag lung Monastery to become a monk when he was six. We believed this was a good choice for him and might protect his life because we lost our first son when he was very young.

After my father passed away, I became responsible for my mother, my two monk brothers, and my youngest brother, as well as my wife, my monk son, and my three daughters (one is divorced and has two sons, and another has a son with her current husband). Given the enormity of my role, I do not gamble or drink. While I have never explicitly promised to abstain from these activities, I recognize that they are detrimental to me and the well-being of my family.

I began herding sheep alone when I was sixteen. Although my father initially accompanied me at our *lug ba* 'sheep herding camp', he would eventually leave for our *zog ba* 'yak herding camp' where my parents tended our yaks and horses. Sometimes Father stayed with me for a day or two before leaving.

I relied solely on my feet to navigate the terrain while herding because I had no horse or yak to ride. Without a calendar, clock, or watch, I relied on the sun's position to determine the time to drive the sheep back to their enclosure. It

was tough, but I thank Father, who taught me self-sufficiency and resilience.

As time passed, my siblings grew older and were able to help herd the sheep while my parents continued to focus on the yaks and horses.

I'm very concerned about my sisters and daughters. I worry about each of them and the kind of man they will end up with. We can no longer arrange marriages as we did in the old days. There are many irresponsible men, at least in Gcig sgril County. They marry someone today and leave them tomorrow. I can accept it if my sisters or daughters marry poor men if they are responsible and kind.

Unfortunately, some of my daughters and sisters have had negative experiences in their marriages, which they certainly did not deserve. I hope that they gained valuable lessons from these experiences.

As family head, my concerns include maintaining a good quality of life and access to suitable grazing land. Additionally, I am anxious about the possibility of any family members falling ill and requiring medical treatment. Maintaining the good health of my family members is paramount.

FIG 21. Tshe brtan in his family home near Stag lung Monastery (2023, 'Jam dbyangs skyabs).

Father gave me his *mchong* after I married Rtse pe and told me:

Before your mother and I married, my family lived in the commune organized by the local government. The *sre chen* had a huge yak hair tent

where people ate together.

The local government instructed families to burn things related to religion. One night, my father, 'Be tho, and some elder men gathered and collected religious items from each family and started to burn them. In the middle of this activity, a man asked my father if our family had any important items in our *g.yang khug*' pouch for auspicious objects' since we were an old family. My father grabbed the half-burnt *g.yang khug* and noticed a heavy item inside. He dropped it to the ground. A *mchong* was inside, which he kept as a *g.yang rten*.¹

My *mchong* is special to me. I respect it as a *g.yang rten*. When I was a child, I had a very important amulet that I lost. I regretted losing it. My parents scolded, "What a bad boy! How could you lose it?"

Father later gave me his *mchong*, which was important to him. I take good care of it because I don't want to lose it like I did my amulet.

Although the *mchong* is an ornament, it means much more to me. Father obtained it from our family's *g.yang khug*. Anything that remains within a *g.yang khug* symbolizes prosperity and good fortune.

I wore a coral necklace when I was younger but eventually gave it to my oldest daughter. People in my and older generations lose interest in ornaments.

CONCLUSION

In 2023, children who were relatives of Mtha' ba Community elders began attending school around the age of six. Material items they most valued were associated with modern technology and fashion, e.g., phones, computers, vehicles, earphones, and certain popular clothing brands. For example, government employees often competed with the clothing they wore. With salaries that would allow it, Arc'teryx² was a widely popular brand in Gcig sgril County.

¹ According to Phyogs las rnam rgyal, *g.yang rten* are certain objects with the power to channel positive energy and good fortune. When venerated, they can bring prosperity, abundance, and success to individuals or communities.

² Created in British Columbia, Canada in the late 1980s as Rock Solid Manufacturing, Arc'teryx is an outdoor wear company. In 2023, Arc'teryx was a global brand with offices in Vancouver, Tokyo, Munich, and other locations. Their clothing is used by hikers, police, and soldiers for its

Arc'teryx clothing was expensive, considered high-quality, and therefore elevated the status of those who wore it.

Only the elders in Don skyid's community consider the items described by Don skyid and others as valuable. The passing of these elders will lead to a time when very few will appreciate such items as described in this article. The younger generation in the community now places greater value on gold necklaces, gold rings, coral, and other fashionable items, to define their identity. While some may view this value shift with concern, it is part of the landscape of rapidly altering cultural norms.

Certain youth valued artifacts because they hoped they might sell them for a high price, unlike elders such as Don skyid, who never considered selling them. When I asked Don skyid, "Have you ever thought about selling your artifacts?" she replied:

No. Nobody has asked me to sell my artifacts. Many think they have little value, but they are very important to me. I feel safe when I wear them and am unhappy when I see my children, grandchildren, and great-grandchildren without items like those I wear. I encourage them to wear such items because they can protect them.

Don skyid and her husband believed that offering incense and spinning the *seng gdong srung bzlog 'khor lo* had an important direct connection to their family's well-being and good fortune. In contrast, their grandchildren and great-grandchildren considered such activities unnecessary. They also had a minimum interest in and appreciation of yak hair tents.

When I spoke with Don skyid, the idea of interviewing Mtha' ba Community elders and writing about their life experiences and beliefs was sparked. I asked Don skyid, "What is the most important thing to you? Why?"

Her response was, "My *thar 'khor*."

This piqued my interest. The values of Don skyid and other elders, such as Bde sgrol, Chos mdzad, and Yi po, differ from those of younger generations who emphasize the value of money, material possessions, and contemporary knowledge production. The beliefs

of the elders, formed through direct interaction with their environment, extensive observations, and long-term experiences, are increasingly devalued and disregarded. Their grandchildren and great-grandchildren do not share the same values and beliefs. With the passing of Don skyid and other elder members, their unique culture and values will be lost. It is a privilege to have had the opportunity to speak with them and write about their experiences and beliefs. Once they are gone, finding Tibetans with first-hand knowledge of traditional Tibetan lifestyles and beliefs will be challenging.

This paper has also explored the religious and cultural practices of the Mtha' ba Community in Amdo through personal experiences and histories of local elder Tibetan religious practitioners. The paper has highlighted the significant roles that religious items and personal ornaments play in the lives of the locals and provided insights into the importance of religion and tradition in the community.

Through the stories of Don skyid, Chos mdzad, Yi po, Bde sgröl, and Tshe brtan, this paper shows how religious items and personal ornaments are not only symbols of faith but also connect individuals to their cultural heritage and history. By examining the *thar 'khor*, *seng gdong srung bzlog 'khor lo*, *sgrol ma'i 'khor lo*, *ma Ni'i 'khor lo*, *'then 'khor* and *mchong 'agate*', this paper offers a deeper understanding of the symbolism, function, and significance of these religious items.

I also want to mention Brox's "What is the Value of a Tibetan Prayer Wheel?" (2022), which explores how the value of a Tibetan prayer wheel is understood and contested by various people based on "conceptual developments in the fields of religion and of technology to develop Jens Beckert's typology of value" (2022:2). This valuable contribution to Tibetan Studies is quite different from my exploration of Tibetan prayer wheels, which showcases the importance of personal experiences and histories in understanding the significance of religious practices and objects in a specific Tibetan community, thus contributing to the literature on Tibetan religion and culture. It offers a unique perspective on the diverse and rich traditions still maintained and practiced in this region,

highlighting the importance of cultural heritage and history in shaping local identity and values.

APPENDIX: MONASTERIES, PLACE NAMES, AND PEOPLE.

Table 1. Monasteries

Name	Background
A bzod Monastery	Located in Sko chen Pastoral Community, Geig sgril County, about 110 kilometers from the county seat, it was established in 1917 by Bla ma Jia guan and Ma De. The mobile monastery was yak hair tents until 1955. In that year, a large earth-wall scripture hall and several monks' quarters were built with the support of the head of the A bzod Tribe, Chos rgyam, and a wandering incarnation <i>bla ma</i> , Rta shul 'gyur med rgya mtsho. The monastery thus expanded to 4 large and small scripture halls, around 50 monks' quarters, 120 monks, and 2 incarnation <i>bla ma</i> . The monastery closed after religious reform in 1958, and most monks resumed secular life. It was later reopened but closed again during the Cultural Revolution (1966-1976). Reopening in 1982, the monastery underwent extensive rebuilding, including a large scripture hall, prayer wheel rooms, corridors, courtyards, and monks' quarters. In 2023, the monastery covered an area of about 300 <i>mu</i> ¹ and is under the jurisdiction of the original Khang rgan a bzod Tribe's tent Monastery (Nian and Bai 1993:280).
Bla rung sgar Monastery	Bdud 'joms rdo rje ² (1935-1904) established Bla rung sgar in 1880. A <i>bshad grwa</i> 'center for teaching' and a small <i>sgrub grwa</i> 'retreat center' were constructed at Bla rung sgar in 1980 (Reb

¹ 300 *mu* = 20 hectares.

² See <https://bit.ly/3zGshmd> 29 March 2023 for more on Bdud 'joms rdo rje.

	gong pa 'jigs med bsam grub 1995:376-378).
Bsu ba Monastery	In 1728, Gnyan rtse dpon slob ngag dbang chos 'phel (1685-1756) founded Dga' ldan bkra shis chos gling that later came to be known as Bsu ba dgon. Bsu ba Monastery is located in Bsu ba Township, Rnga ba (Aba) County, Rnga ba Tibetan and Qiang Autonomous Prefecture, Si khron (Sichuan) Province. ¹
D+hIHphu Monastery	D+hIHphu Monastery was established in 1844 by Sde nang sku chen kun dga' rgyal mtshan. It is located in D+he ku Township, Rnga ba County.
Dga' ldan Monastery	In 1409, Tsong kha pa blo bzang grags pa (1357-1419) established Dga' ldan Monastery located approximately 30 miles east of Lhasa City (Dga' ldan dgon pa dang brag yer pa'i lo rgyus 1991:5). ²
Rdo grub chen Monastery	Rdo grub chen Monastery was established in 1852 by 'Jigs med phun tshogs 'byung gnas (1824-1864) (Reb gong pa 'jigs med bsam grub 1995:337-338).
Sgo mang Monastery	In 1790, Kun mkhyen sku 'phreng gnyis pa rje btsan dkon mchog 'jigs med dbang bo (1728-1791) founded Sgo mang Monastery, also known as Mdo smad rnga yul sgo mang dgon bshad sgrub 'phel rgyas gling (Ldong yon tan rgya mtsho 2000:32-44). ³
Stag lung Monastery	Stag lung dgon ka dag spros bral gling (De he long kong xing yuan li xi lun zhou) is in Stag lung Valley, Khang sar Township in the south of Gcig sgril County, 6 kilometers from the county town. It was founded by Bstan pa'i dbang phyug and Tshul khrim bzang po in 1983 (Nian and Bai 1993:279).

¹ For more about Bsu ba Monastery, see <https://bit.ly/3KMpDlJ> 9 April 2023.

² For more on Dga' ldan Monastery, see <https://bit.ly/3ZQsKxd> 7 April 2023.

³ For more on Sgo mang Monastery, see <https://bit.ly/3fGMSAP> 12 November 2022.

	Rdza mu ra sprul sku ¹ taught based on merging Gsar ma, Rnying ma, and Jo nang schools in a <i>nag sgar</i> 'nomad tent monastic community' that moved with the local Khang sar Tribe. In 1942, some Gsar ma followers separated from the <i>nag sgar</i> and built a temple in Dpon lung Valley, Smin thang Township Town. The ruins of this temple are visible today. Bstan pa'i dbang phyug ² and his nephew, Tshul khrim bzang po (b. 1946), built a new Stag lung dgon ka dag spros bral gling in about 1982. In 1983, the monastery had 21 monks and <i>bla ma</i> . In 2022, there were about 300 monks and <i>bla ma</i> . ³
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Table 2. Place names

Name	Location
A bzod	a Sog ru Township community
Dbon pa	a community in Sgo mang (Gemo) Township, Rnga ba County
Gcig sgril	a county in Mgo log Prefecture
Gsa' khog	an area in Khang sar Township
Khang sar	a township in Gcig sgril County
Lha sa	capital of the Tibet Autonomous Region
Mgo log	an autonomous prefecture in Mtsho sngon Province
Mtha' ba	a community near Stag lung Monastery
Mtsho sngon	a province in northwest China
Pad+ma	Pad+ma County
Rnga ba	Rnga ba County
Si khron	a province adjoining Mtsho sngon

¹ 1918-1958. For more, see <https://bit.ly/3b78a8v> 27 July 2022 and <https://bit.ly/3PSqXTA> 27 July 2022.

² Khang sar bstan pa'i dbang phyug 1938-2014; <https://bit.ly/3Bln6dU> 27 July 2022.

³ Based on oral interviews with two monks at Stag lung Monastery (Phyogs las rnam rgyal and Thub chos) in 2022. For photos, see Gtsang rigs skal bzang rnam 'dren (2019:114-153) and Smith (2017:149).

Smin thang	a township in Gcig sgril County
Sog ru	a township in Gcig sgril County
Spen ma	Spen ma Valley, Khang sar Township

Table 3. People.

Name	Background
'Be tho	Bsod dar's (1943-2016) father
'Jam dbyangs skyabs (Jiayangjian)	the author
'Jigs phun (b. 2015)	son of Mi 'gyur and Phyug mtsho
'Phrin las rgya mtsho (19??-1970)	Bsod dar's cousin
A khu bkra phun (1946-2020)	a <i>bla ma</i> from A bzod Monastery
A khu blos tshul	a monk who was once a <i>mkhan po</i> in Rdo grub chen
A khu stag lha (1945-2018)	a doctor and a <i>bla ma</i>
Bde sgrol (b. 1947)	<i>yig brgya'i 'khor lo</i> belongs to her, a <i>dge bsnyen ma</i> , and the focus of Part 6
Bde skyid	Bde skyid was 'Be tho's sister. They had four siblings.
Blo brtan	a horse herder of Sgo mang Monastery known as Rgya rag because of his thick beard
Blo ldan	'Be tho's brother. They had four siblings.
Bsod dar (1943-2016)	Don skyid's husband.
Bstan pa'i dbang phyug (1938-2014)	founded Stag lung dgon ka dag spros bral gling in 1983 (Nian and Bai 1993:279)
Chos mdzad (b. 1938)	Yi po's (b. 1941) husband
Dkar dbang	Khang sar Tribal leader
Dkon bsam (1953~2005)	Bde sgrol's husband
Dme shul bza' shar ba	Bsod dar's great grandmother

Dme sman	Dme shul bza' shar ba's husband
Don skyid (b. 1946)	Bsod dar's wife
Dpal ldan skyid	Tshe brtan's daughter
G.yang phyug	Tshe brtan's daughter
G.yang res (b. 1990)	Don skyid's granddaughter
Gshin rje chos rgyal	the Lord of Death
Hwar ba a lags (b. 1948)	the head <i>bla ma</i> of Sgo mang Monastery
Jigme Puntsok, 'Jigs med phun tshogs, Chos rje yid bzhin nor bu, Khenpo Jigme Puntsok, Mkhan po 'jigs med phun tshogs (1933-2004)	He developed Bla rung sgar (Larung gar, Si khron), a Buddhist Mountain retreat focused on Buddhist teachings in the 1980s.
Kho lo	wife of Dkar dbang
Khra bza' sher mtsho	'Be tho's wife
Khya bza'	an alternative name for Kho lo
Khya dge a legs	According to Don skyid, he was a <i>bla ma</i> from Sgo mang Monastery who did not wear monastic robes, was married, had several children, and was a good <i>bla ma</i> and <i>mo pa</i> 'diviner'.
King of Rme'u (1916-1966)	Born in Rnga ba, Dpal mgon 'phrin las rab brtan (Pelgon Trinle Rabten) was the last King of the Meu Kingdom. His mother, Queen Dpal chen don grub mtsho (Pelchen Dondrub Tso), ruled the kingdom until Rabten came of age. ¹
Lcam gyi bra bo	A bzod Tribe male deity
Lcam gyi bra mo	A bzod Tribe female deity
Mgo tshul	a relative of Dkar dbang and living in 2023

¹ <https://bit.ly/3U6DaXd> 4 November 2022.

Mi 'gyur (b. 1983)	Chos mdzad and Yi po's adopted son
Myang lu	found Don skyid's <i>thar 'khor</i>
PaN chen rin po che (1938-1989)	the 10 th PaN chen <i>bla ma</i>
Phur ba (b. 1954)	Don skyid's brother
Phyag 'tshal a lags or Bsod nams rdo rje (b. 1971)	a Stag lung Monastery <i>bla ma</i>
Phyogs las rnam rgyal (b. 1971)	Don skyid's oldest monk son
Phyug mtsho (b. 1985)	Mi 'gyur's wife
Rab brtan (1944-1999)	Don skyid's brother
Rgya rag	Blo brtan's nickname
Ri lo	a blacksmith
Ri yongs dga' ldan	Dga' ldan Monastery in Lha sa sent him to our community. He arrived in the 1950s (Don skyid).
Rnam grol	Bde sgrol's brother
Rong dpal	A khu blos tshul's brother
Rtse pe (b. 1965)	Don skyid's daughter-in-law
Sher mtsho (1901-1983)	Don skyid's mother
Sman lha	Dme shul bza' shar ba's husband was also known as Dme sman
Snang gsal rgya mtsho (b. 1987)	Don skyid's second monk son
Tho skyid	'Be tho's sister
Thub chos (b. 1963)	a monk from Stag lung Monastery
Tshe brtan (b. 1968)	Bsod dar and Don skyid's oldest son
Tshul khirms bzang po (b. 1946)	Bstan pa'i dbang phyug's nephew
Ye shes dzang po (b. 1996)	Tshe brtan and Rtse pe's son
Yi po (b. 1941)	Chos mdzad's wife

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TIBETAN TERMS

'be tho འབེ་ཐོ།	ཨ་ཁུ་སྐུ་ཚུལ།
'dre འདྲེ།	a khu stag lha ཨ་ཁུ་སྐུ་ག་ལ།
'jam dbyangs skyabs འཇམ་དབྱངས་སྐུབས།	a mdo ཨ་མདོ།
'jigs phun འཇིགས་ལུན།	bcu tshad བར་ཚད།
'khor lo འཁོར་ལོ།	bde sgrol བདེ་སྐྱོལ།
'khor lo'i yu ba འཁོར་ལོའི་ཡུ་བ།	bde skyid བདེ་སྐྱིད།
'khor lte འཁོར་ལྗེ།	bka' 'gyur བཀའ་འགྲུབ།
'khor rdo འཁོར་རྩོ།	bla ma ལྷ་མ།
'khor thag འཁོར་ཐག།	bla rung sgar ལྷ་རུང་སྐར།
'khor yo འཁོར་ཡོ།	blo brtan ལྷོ་བརྟན།
'og lte འོག་ལྗེ།	blo ldan ལྷོ་ལྗན།
'phrin las rgya mtsho འཕྲིན་ལས་རྒྱ་མཚོ།	bshas sha བཤམ་ཤ།
'then 'khor འཐེན་འཁོར།	bsod dar བསོད་དར།
'then lung འཐེན་ལུང།	bstan pa'i dbang phyug བསྐྱེད་པའི་དབང་ལྷུག།
a bzo ཨ་བཙོང།	bsu ba བསུ་བ།
a khu bkra phun ཨ་ཁུ་བརྒྱ་ལུན།	btags grol བཏགས་གྲོལ།
a khu blos tshul ཨ་ཁུ་བློ་ཚུལ།	bu rgyus sbra ring tshang བུ་རྒྱལ་སྐུ་རིང་ཚང།

bu rgyus sbra ring tshang gi
sbra red rgya shar ba 'bab
sa red

བུ་རྒྱུས་སྤྱི་རིང་ཚང་གི་སྤྱི་རེད།
སྤྱི་ཤར་བ་འབབ་ས་འེད།

bye lcags བྱེ་ལྷགས།

bye ma ka ra བྱེ་མ་ཀ་ར།

byang chub sgröl ma

བྱང་ཚུབ་སྐྱོལ་མ།

chod 'og tu 'phangs pa

ཚོད་འོག་ཏུ་འཕངས་པ།

chod nag la shor ba

ཚོད་ནག་ལ་ཤོར་བ།

chos mdzad ཚོས་མཛད།

chos rje yid bzhin nor bu ཚོས་རྗེ་

ཡིད་བཞིན་ནོར་བུ།

chung sri རྒྱུང་སྤྱི།

D+hIHphu ལྷིམ་ཕུ།

dbon pa དབོན་པ།

dbyar gnas དབྱར་གནས།

dga' ldan དགའ་ལྷན།

dkar dbang དཀར་དབང་།

dkon bsam དཀོན་བསམ།

dme shul bza' shar ba

དམེ་ཤལ་བཟའ་ཤར་བ།

dme sman དམེ་སྐྱམ།

don skyid རོན་སྐྱིད།

dong tse རོང་ཙེ།

dpon lung དཔོན་ལུང་།

dung dkar དུང་དཀར།

g.yang khug གཡང་ཁུག།

g.yang res གཡང་རེས།

g.yang rten གཡང་རྟེན།

gcig sgril གཅིག་སྐྱེལ།

gcod གཙོང།

gdon གདོན།

gdon bgegs གདོན་བགོགས།

gdugs གདུགས།

gnam 'khor lo rtse dgu གནམ་འཁོར་

ལོ་རྩེ་དགུ།

gsa' khog གསའ་ཁོག།

gsar ma གསར་མ།

gshin rje chos rgyal

གཤེན་རྗེ་ཚོས་རྒྱལ།

gto bla གཏོ་བླ།

hwar ba a lags

ཏུར་བ་ཨ་ལགས།

Jigme Puntsok, 'jigs med

phun tshogs འཇིགས་མེད་ཕུན་ཚོགས།

jo nang རྫོན་ང།

khang sar ཁང་སར།

Khenpo, mkhan po

མཁན་པོ།

kho lo ཁོ་ལོ།

khra bza' sher mtsho

ཁྲ་བཟའ་ཤེར་མཚོ།

khri ka, Trika ཁྲི་ཀ།

khya bza' ལྷ་བཟའ།

khya dge a legs

ལྷ་དགེ་ཨ་ལགས།

klad nag ལྗང་ནག།

la nye ལ་ཉེ།

Larung Gar, bla rung sgar ལྷ་རུང་

སྐར།

lcam gyi bra bo ལམ་གྱི་བལ་བོ།

lcam gyi bra mo ལམ་གྱི་བལ་མོ།

lha sa ལྷ་ས།

lug ba ལུག་བ།

lug ba'i sbra ལུག་བའི་སྤྱ།

lung ring ལུང་རིང་།

ma Ni'i 'khor lo

མ་ཉིའཁོར་ལོ།

ma Ni མ་ཉེ།

mchong མཚོང་།

mdud pa མདུད་པ།
mdung dar smug po can

མདུང་དར་སྐྱུག་པོ་ཅན།

mdung dar smug po

མདུང་དར་སྐྱུག་པོ།

mdzo མཚོ།

mdzo stag stag dung rked

can མཚོ་སྐྱུག་སྐྱུག་དུང་ཀེད་ཅན།

mgo log མགོ་ལོག།

mgo tshul མགོ་ཚུལ།

mi 'gyur མི་འགྲུང།

mkhan po མཁན་པོ།

mo pa མོ་པ།

mtha' ba མཐའ་བ།

mtsher shul མཚོར་གུལ།

mtsho sngon མཚོ་སྒོན།

myang lu མྱང་ལུ།

nag po dgu sbyor

ནག་པོ་དགུ་སྟོར།

nag sgar ནག་སྐར།

nag tshang ནག་ཚང།

ni'i 'khor lo མིའི་འཁོར་ལོ།

nyal sbra ཉལ་སྐྱ།

oM a mi de wa hrIH

ཨོ་ཨ་མི་དེ་ལ་ཧྲིཿ།

pad+ma པདྨ།

paN chen པཎ་ཅེན།

paN chen rin po che

པཎ་ཅེན་རིན་པོ་ཅེ།

phur ba ཕུར་བ།

phur ma ཕུར་མ།

phyag 'tshal a lags

ཕྱག་མཚལ་ཨ་ལགས།

phye ཕྱེ།

phyogs las rnam rgyal

ཕྱོགས་ལས་རྣམ་རྒྱལ།

phyug mtsho ཕྱུག་མཚོ།

pra pa བྲ་པ།

rab brtan རབ་བརྟན།

rag khrom 'khor lo

རག་ཁྲོམ་འཁོར་ལོ།

rdo grub chen རྩ་གུབ་ཆེན།

rdo rje རྩ་རྗེ།

rdza mu ra sprul sku རྩ་མུ་ར་སྐྱུལ་སྐུ།

rgya rag རྒྱ་རག།

ri lo རི་ལོ།

ri yongs dga' ldan

རི་ཡོངས་དགའ་ལྷན།

ril bu རིལ་བུ།

rme'u རྩེའུ།

rnam grol རྣམ་གྲོ།

rnga ba ར་བ།

rnying ma རྩིང་མ།

rong dpal རོང་དཔལ།

rta bra bra ར་བ་བ་བ།

rtsam pa རུས་པ།

rtse pe རེ་ཤེ།

rtsis pa རུམ་པ།

sa pad+ma 'dab brgyad

ས་པདྨ་འདབ་བརྟན།

sbra gso སྐྱ་གསོ།

sbra leb སྐྱ་ལེབ།

sde dge སྡེ་དགེ།

seng gdong srung bzlog 'khor

lo རེང་གདོང་སྲུང་བརྗོག་

འཁོར་ལོ།

ser lo སེར་ལོ།

sgar gyi phreng ba

སྐར་གྱི་ཕྱེང་བ།

sgo mang སྐོ་མང།

sgrol ma'i 'khor lo

སྐོལ་མའི་འཁོར་ལོ།

sher mtsho ཤེར་མཚོ།

shi sha ཤི་ཤ།

shi tshigs ཤི་ཚེགས།
si khron སི་ཁྲོན།
sked thag སྐད་ཐག།
skye rgyud སྐྱེ་རྒྱུད།
sman lha སྐུན་ལྷ།
smin thang སྐུན་ཐང་།
snang gsal rgya mtsho
 སྐང་གསལ་རྒྱ་མཚོ།
sog ru སོག་རུ།
spen ma སྤེན་མ།
spen ma'i g.yu rgyal
 phyug mo
 སྤེན་མའི་གཡུ་རྒྱལ་ཡུག་མོ།
sre chen སྤེ་ཚེན།
srog shing སྤོག་ཤིང་།
srung 'khor སྤུང་འཁོར་།
stag lung dgon ka dag
spros bral gling སྤྲོག་ཕུང་དགོན་ཀ་དག་རྩོམ་
 བལ་གླིང་།

stag lung སྤྲོག་ཕུང་།
steng lte སྤེང་ལྗེ།
thar 'khor ཐར་འཁོར།
thar mdo ཐར་མདོ།
tho skyid ཐོ་སྦྱིད།
thub chos ཐུབ་ཚོས།
tog ཏོག།
tshe brtan ཚེ་བརྟན།
tshogs sbra ཚོགས་སྤྲེ།
tshul khriims bzang po
 ཚུལ་ཁྲིམས་བཟང་པོ།
ye shes dzang po
 ཡེ་ཤེས་བཟང་པོ།
yi po ཡི་པོ།
yig brgya ཡིག་བརྒྱ།
zha ye ཇམ་ཡེ།
zhe dgu ཇེ་དགུ།
zi ling ཟེ་ལིང་།
zog ba ཟོག་བ།

CHINESE TERMS

Aba 阿坝
Dongfeng 东风
Gemo 格莫
gongshe 公社
Guoluo 果洛
Guide 贵德
Hanzi 汉子

Jiaguan 加官
Jiayangjian 加羊尖
Jiuzhi 久治
Ma De 玛德
Qinghai 青海
Sichuan 四川
Xining 西宁